

Analytical Solutions of Klein-Gordon Equation using Elzaki-Adomian Decomposition Method

Raifu S. Ajayi¹ & Balogun Joseph¹

¹Department of Mathematics and Computer Science, Nigeria Police Academy, Wudil Kano State Nigeria.

Abstract:- In this paper, the Elzaki-Adomian Decomposition Method (EADM) is employed to derive analytical solutions for both homogeneous and non-homogeneous Klein-Gordon equations. This method synergistically integrates two powerful techniques: the Elzaki transform and the Adomian decomposition method. Through the combination of these methods, the study effectively addresses the complexities of solving such differential equations. The application of EADM is demonstrated by solving two distinct cases of homogeneous linear Klein-Gordon equations and two cases of non-homogeneous linear Klein-Gordon equations. These specific examples highlight the versatility and efficiency of EADM in handling various forms of the Klein-Gordon equation. The method's ability to quickly converge to accurate analytical solutions is a testament to its robustness and reliability. EADM proves particularly advantageous due to its high rate of convergence, which significantly reduces the computational effort and time required to achieve precise solutions. The results obtained from the study confirm the method's potential to provide reliable and fast analytical solutions, reinforcing its applicability and effectiveness and reliable means of obtaining analytical solutions, making it a significant contribution to the field of differential equation analysis in applied mathematics.

Keywords: Linear Klein-Gordon equation, Elzaki Transform, Elzaki-Adomian Decomposition method, Analytical Solutions.

Email: callrasajayi@gmail.com

Received: January 18, 2024

Revised: March 2, 2024

Accepted: March 21, 2024

Cite this Paper as: R. S. Ajayi and J. Balogun, "Analytical Solutions of Klein-Gordon Equation using Elzaki-Adomian Decomposition Method," *Science Journal of Applied and Natural Sciences*, vol. 3, no. 1, pp. 64-78, 30 March 2024.

About the Journal: SJANS is a multidisciplinary science journal and the official journal of the Faculty of Science, Nigeria Police Academy, Kano, Nigeria

1.0 Introduction

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Mathematical phenomenon have important effects on applied mathematics, physics, and

courses related to engineering; many of such physical phenomena are modeled in real-life problems resulting in functional equations, such as the linear Klein-Gordon equation of the form: Ahmadov *et al* 2024

$$U_{tt}(x, t) - U_{xx}(x, t) + aU(x, t) = h(x, t) \tag{1}$$

With initial conditions;

$$U(x, 0) = f(x), U_t(x, 0) = g(x). \tag{2}$$

This equation was named after two physicists Oskar Klein and Walter Gordon, who introduced the equation in 1926 to describe relativistic electrons. The equation appears in many areas such as relativistic physics, quantum field theory, dispersive wave-phenomena, plasma physics, and applied physical sciences. Diverse methods have

been used by several researchers to handle this equation. Recently, Mohammad et al., (2024) presented numerical estimation of the fractional Klein-Gordon equation with Discrete Chebyshev Polynomials, Falade (2022) proposed and applied a newly formulated algorithm for the numerical solution of nonlinear Klein-Gordon equation. Similarly, we reference the works in (Hashim

(Print) ISSN 3027-284X

Online: E-ISSN 3026-9245

et al., 2023;Srinivasa et al., 2024;Onyenegecha et al., 2021;Bilal et al., 2024; Khan et al., 2019;Kumar, 2022;Ahmadov et al., 2024; Emmanuel and Idu, 2024).

Elzaki transform and the Adomian decomposition method. The reliability of LADM led to the development of EADM and has been successfully used by Hussein (2024) to solve nonlinear fractional differential equations with the Caputo-Fabrizio fractional operator. Orapine et al., (2022) also applied EADM to get analytical solutions of some special nonlinear partial differential equation. In this paper, we apply EADM to the general linear Klein-Gordon equation and then use the results to solve some illustrating examples and obtain their analytical solutions.

Another method that is important and has received more attention by several researchers is the Laplace-Adomian decomposition method (LAMD). This method was first introduced by Suheil A. (Khuri, 2001). Although, many researchers including the likes of (Adewale et al., 2024; Olayiwola et al., 2024; and Yunus et al., 2024) has worked extensively with LADM, however, a new method was introduced recently by Ige et al., (2019) known as the Elzaki-Adomian decomposition method (EADM). This method combines two well-known and high-powered methods, the

2.0 ILLUSTRATION OF ELZAKI TRANSFORM

The Elzaki transform defined for function of exponential order (Elzaki, 2011). Consider the function in the set F defined as:

$$F = \left\{ f(t) : \exists M, C_1, C_2 > 0. |f(t)| < M e^{\frac{|t|}{C_1}} \text{ if } t \in (-1)^i \times [0, \infty) \right\} \tag{3}$$

where for any given function in the set F defined above, the constants C_1, C_2 may be either finite or infinite, but M must be

infinite. Then the Elzaki transform is defined as;

$$F(s) = E[f(t)] = s \int_0^\infty f(t) e^{-t/s} dt, \quad t \geq s \in (C_1, C_2) \tag{4}$$

where E is the Elzaki transform operator. In practice, when one applies the Elzaki transform to an equation, one has to at some point invert the Elzaki transform by finding the function $f(t)$ which corresponds to some specified $F(s)$. The function $f(t)$ is called the inverse Elzaki transform of $F(s)$ and will be denoted as:

If we use the definition of Elzaki transform of equations (4) on some functions that are useful when applying on linear Klein-Gordon Equation, we have;

$$f(t) = E^{-1}[F(s)] \tag{5}$$

2.1 Elzaki Transform of Partial Derivatives

where E^{-1} is the inverse operators respectively.

We find the Elzaki transform of the following partial derivatives express below by using integration by parts.

i. $E(U(x, t)) = s \int_0^\infty e^{-t/s} U(x, t) dt.$

- ii. $E(U_t(x, t)) = s \int_0^\infty e^{-t/s} U_t(x, t) dt = s^{-1}E(U(x, t)) - sU(x, 0).$
- iii. $E(U_{tt}(x, t)) = s \int_0^\infty e^{-t/s} U_{tt}(x, t) dt = s^{-2}E(U(x, t)) - U(x, 0) - sU_t(x, 0).$
- iv. $E(U_x(x, t)) = s \int_0^\infty e^{-t/s} U_x(x, t) dt = \frac{d}{dx}E(U(x, t)).$
- v. $E(U_{xx}(x, t)) = s \int_0^\infty e^{-t/s} U_{xx}(x, t) dt = \frac{d^2}{dx^2}E(U(x, t)).$

2.2 Elzaki Transform of basic Functions

Some of the Elzaki transform of basic functions which are useful to this paper, are considered

in table1.

Table 1: Table of basic Functions and their Elzaki Transform

F(t)	E[f(t)]=F(s)
a	$E(a) = as^2$
t^n	$E(t^n) = n! s^{n+2}$
e^{at}	$E[e^{at}] = \frac{s^2}{1 - as}$
e^{-at}	$E[e^{-at}] = \frac{s^2}{1 + as}$
$Cosat$	$E(Cosat) = \frac{s^2}{1 + a^2s^2}$
$Sinat$	$E(Sinat) = \frac{as^3}{1 + a^2s^2}$
$Coshat$	$E(Coshat) = \frac{s^2}{1 - a^2s^2}$
$Sinhat$	$E(Sinhat) = \frac{as^3}{1 - a^2s^2}$

3.0 METHODOLOGY

We consider the general linear Klein-Gordon equation given in equation (1) with

initial conditions in equation (2). Then, we apply the Elzaki transform to equation (1) to get;

$$s^{-2}E(U(x, t)) - U(x, 0) - sU_t(x, 0) - \frac{d^2}{dx^2}E(U(x, t)) + aE(U(x, t)) = E(u(x, t)) \quad (6)$$

We then use the initial condition to get;

$$s^{-2}E(U(x, t)) = f(x) + sg(x) + E(U(x, t)) + \frac{d^2}{dx^2}E(U(x, t)) - aE(U(x, t)) \quad (7)$$

On multiplying through equation (7) by s^2 , we get;

$$E(U(x, t)) = s^2 f(x) + s^3 g(x) + s^2 E(U(x, t)) + s^2 \frac{d^2}{dx^2} E(U(x, t)) - as^2 E(U(x, t)) \quad (8)$$

By definition, the Adomian decomposition is given as

$$U(x, t) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} U_n(x, t) \quad (9)$$

Substituting equation (9) into equation (8), we get;

$$E \left[\sum_0^{\infty} U_n(x, t) \right] = s^2 f(x) + s^3 g(x) + s^2 E(U(x, t)) + s^2 \frac{d^2}{dx^2} E[\sum_0^{\infty} U_n(x, t)] - as^2 E\{\sum_0^{\infty} U_n(x, t)\} \quad (10)$$

But

$$E[\sum_0^{\infty} U_n(x, t)] = E[\sum_{-1}^{\infty} U_{n+1}(x, t)] = E(U_0(x, t)) + E[\sum_0^{\infty} U_{n+1}(x, t)] \quad (11)$$

Thus

$$E(U_0(x, t)) + E \left[\sum_0^{\infty} U_{n+1}(x, t) \right] = s^2 f(x) + s^3 g(x) + s^2 E(U(x, t)) + s^2 \frac{d^2}{dx^2} E \sum_0^{\infty} U_n(x, t) - as^2 E\{\sum_0^{\infty} U_n(x, t)\}. \quad (12)$$

On comparing both sides of equation (12) we get;

$$E(U_0(x, t)) = s^2 f(x) + s^3 g(x) + s^2 E(u(x, t)) \quad (13)$$

and we obtain a recurrence equation, given as;

$$E[\sum_0^{\infty} U_{n+1}(x, t)] = s^2 \frac{d^2}{dx^2} E \sum_0^{\infty} U_n(x, t) - as^2 E\{\sum_0^{\infty} U_n(x, t)\}. \quad (14)$$

We apply the inverse Elzaki transform to equation (13) to get $U_0(x, t)$ and then we start to evaluate from the recurrence equation (14) at $n=1,2,3,4,\dots$ and applying the inverse

Elzaki transform respectively, to get: $u_1(x, t), u_2(x, t), u_3(x, t), \dots$. Therefore, we get the solution in the form of infinite series as

$$U(x, t) = U_0(x, t) + U_1(x, t) + U_2(x, t) + U_3(x, t) + \dots \quad (15)$$

4.0 NUMERICAL EXAMPLES

In this section, we consider four examples to demonstrate the efficiency of the Elzaki-Adomian Transform Method (EADM) presented in the last section.

Example 1. Consider the homogeneous Klein–Gordon equation of the form:

$$U_{tt}(x, t) - U_{xx}(x, t) - U(x, t) = 0 \quad (16)$$

with initial conditions;

$$U(x, 0) = 1 + \sin x, U_t(x, 0) = 0. \tag{17}$$

On comparing example one to the general linear Klein-Gordon equation, we get;

$$a = -1, u(x, t) = 0, f(x) = 1 + \sin x \text{ and } g(x) = 0$$

On substituting the values of $a, h(x, t), f(x)$ and $g(x)$ into equation (13) and (14) we get;

$$E(U_0(x, t)) = s^2(1 + \sin x) + s^3(0) + s^2E(0) = s^2 \sin x + s^2 \tag{18}$$

And the recurrence equation becomes

$$E[\sum_0^\infty U_{n+1}(x, t)] = s^2 \frac{d^2}{dx^2} E \sum_0^\infty U_n(x, t) + s^2 E\{\sum_0^\infty U_n(x, t)\} \tag{19}$$

Applying the inverse Elzaki transform to equation (18), we get;

$$U_0(x, t) = E^{-1}(s^2 \sin x + s^2) = \sin x + 1 \tag{20}$$

Now, we compute the individual term from the recurrence equation (19):

when $n=0$, we get;

$$E\{U_1(x, t)\} = s^2 \frac{d^2}{dx^2} E\{U_0(x, t)\} + s^2 E\{U_0(x, t)\} \tag{21}$$

Substituting equation (18) into equation (21), we get;

$$\begin{aligned} E\{U_1(x, t)\} &= s^2 \frac{d^2}{dx^2} (s^2 \sin x + s^2) + s^2 (s^2 \sin x + s^2) \\ &= s^2 (-s^2 \sin x) + s^4 \sin x + s^4 = s^4 \end{aligned} \tag{22}$$

Applying the inverse Elzaki transform to equation (22), we get;

$$U_1(x, t) = E^{-1}(s^4) = \frac{t^2}{2!} \tag{23}$$

when $n=1$, we get;

$$E\{U_2(x, t)\} = s^2 \frac{d^2}{dx^2} E\{U_1(x, t)\} + s^2 E\{U_1(x, t)\} \tag{24}$$

Substituting equation (22) into equation (24), we get;

$$E\{U_2(x, t)\} = s^2 \frac{d^2}{dx^2} (s^4) + s^2 (s^4) = s^6 \tag{25}$$

Applying the inverse Elzaki transform to equation (25), we get;

$$U_2(x, t) = E^{-1}(s^6) = \frac{t^4}{4!} \tag{26}$$

when $n=2$, we get;

$$E\{U_3(x, t)\} = s^2 \frac{d^2}{dx^2} E\{U_2(x, t)\} + s^2 E\{U_2(x, t)\} \tag{27}$$

Substituting equation (25) into equation (27), we get;

$$E\{U_3(x, t)\} = s^2 \frac{d^2}{dx^2} (s^6) + s^2 (s^6) = s^8 \tag{28}$$

Applying the inverse Elzaki transform to equation (28), we get;

$$U_3(x, t) = E^{-1}(s^8) = \frac{t^6}{6!} \tag{29}$$

Similarly other terms can be computed. Therefore, the solution of equation (16) is

$$\begin{aligned} U(x, t) &= U_0(x, t) + U_1(x, t) + U_2(x, t) + U_3(x, t) + U_4(x, t) + \dots \\ &= \sin x + 1 + \frac{t^2}{2!} + \frac{t^4}{4!} + \frac{t^6}{6!} + \frac{t^8}{8!} + \dots = \sin x + \cos ht \end{aligned} \tag{30}$$

Thus, the EADM solution is given as $U(x, t) = \sin x + \cos ht$

Table 2: Numerical solution for example1

$U(x, t)$	Exact solution	EADM solution
0,0	1.000000000000000	1.000000000000000
0.2,0.2	1.21873608641414	1.21873608641414
0.4,0.4	1.47049071414710	1.47049071414710
0.6,0.6	1.75010769163730	1.75010769163730
0.8,0.8	2.05479103720436	2.05479103720436
1.0,1.0	2.38455161962314	2.38455161962314
1.2,1.2	2.74269465329160	2.74269465329160
1.4,1.4	3.13634819538160	3.13634819538160
1.6,1.6	3.57703807423640	3.57703807423640
1.8,1.8	4.08132080719546	4.08132080719546
2.0,2.0	4.67149311790931	4.67149311790931

Figure 1: Graphical solution of example 1

Example 2. Consider the non-homogeneous linear Klein–Gordon equation of the form

$$U_{tt}(x, t) - U_{xx}(x, t) - U(x, t) = 2\cos x \tag{31}$$

with initial conditions;

$$U(x, 0) = 0, U_t(x, 0) = 1 + \cos x. \tag{32}$$

On comparing this example to the general linear Klein-Gordon equation, we get;

$$a = -1, h(x, t) = 2\cos x, f(x) = 0 \text{ and } g(x) = 1 + \cos x$$

Similarly, on substituting the values of $a, h(x, t), f(x)$ and $g(x)$ into equation (13) and (14) we get;

$$\begin{aligned} E(U_0(x, t)) &= s^2(0) + s^3(1 + \cos x) + s^2E(2\cos x) \\ &= 2s^4\cos x + s^3 + s^3\cos x \end{aligned} \tag{33}$$

And the recurrence equation becomes

$$E[\sum_0^\infty U_{n+1}(x, t)] = s^2 \frac{d^2}{dx^2} E \sum_0^\infty U_n(x, t) + s^2 E \{ \sum_0^\infty U_n(x, t) \} \tag{34}$$

Applying the inverse Elzaki transform to equation (33), we get;

$$U_0(x, t) = E^{-1}(2s^4\cos x + s^3 + s^3\cos x) = t^2\cos x + t\cos x + t \tag{35}$$

Now, we compute the individual term from the recurrence equation (34):
when $n=0$, we get;

$$E\{U_1(x, t)\} = s^2 \frac{d^2}{dx^2} E\{U_0(x, t)\} + s^2 E\{U_0(x, t)\} \tag{36}$$

Substituting equation (33) into equation (36), we get;

$$\begin{aligned} E\{U_1(x, t)\} &= s^2 \frac{d^2}{dx^2} (2s^4 \cos x + s^3 + s^3 \cos x) + s^2 (2s^4 \cos x + s^3 + s^3 \cos x) \\ &= s^2 (-2s^4 \cos x - s^3 \cos x) + 2s^6 \cos x + s^5 + s^5 \cos x = s^5 \end{aligned} \tag{37}$$

Applying the inverse Elzaki transform to equation (37), we get;

$$U_1(x, t) = E^{-1}(s^5) = \frac{t^3}{3!} \tag{38}$$

when n=1, we get;

$$E\{U_2(x, t)\} = s^2 \frac{d^2}{dx^2} E\{U_1(x, t)\} + s^2 E\{U_1(x, t)\} \tag{39}$$

Substituting equation (37) into equation (39), we get;

$$E\{U_2(x, t)\} = s^2 \frac{d^2}{dx^2} (s^5) + s^2 (s^5) = s^7 \tag{40}$$

Applying the inverse Elzaki transform to equation (40), we get;

$$U_2(x, t) = E^{-1}(s^7) = \frac{t^5}{5!} \tag{41}$$

when n=2, we get;

$$E\{U_3(x, t)\} = s^2 \frac{d^2}{dx^2} E\{U_2(x, t)\} + s^2 E\{U_2(x, t)\} \tag{42}$$

Substituting equation (40) into equation (42), we get;

$$E\{U_3(x, t)\} = s^2 \frac{d^2}{dx^2} (s^7) + s^2 (s^7) = s^9 \tag{43}$$

Applying the inverse Elzaki transform to equation (43), we get;

$$U_3(x, t) = E^{-1}(s^9) = \frac{t^7}{7!} \tag{44}$$

Similarly other terms can be computed. Hence, the solution of equation (31) becomes

$$\begin{aligned} U(x, t) &= U_0(x, t) + U_1(x, t) + U_2(x, t) + U_3(x, t) + U_4(x, t) + \dots \\ &= t^2 \cos x + t \cos x + t + \frac{t^3}{3!} + \frac{t^5}{5!} + \frac{t^7}{7!} + \dots \\ &= t^2 \cos x + t \cos x + \sinh t = t \cos x (t + 1) + \sinh t \end{aligned} \tag{45}$$

Thus, the EADM solution is given as $U(x, t) = t \cos x(t + 1) + \sin ht$

Table 3: Numerical solution for example 2

$U(x, t)$	Exact solution	EADM solution
0,0	0.0000000000000000	0.0000000000000000
0.2,0.2	0.436551981222992	0.436551981222992
0.4,0.4	0.926546482444431	0.926546482444431
0.6,0.6	1.428975772461530	1.428975772461530
0.8,0.8	1.891363643647540	1.891363643647540
1.0,1.0	2.255805805380080	2.255805805380080
1.2,1.2	2.466085827230590	2.466085827230590
1.4,1.4	2.475391101596340	2.475391101596340
1.6,1.6	2.254097940426870	2.254097940426870
1.8,1.8	1.797075730842520	1.797075730842520
2.0,2.0	1.129979388564170	1.129979388564170

Figure 2: Graphical solution of example 2

Example 3. Consider the homogeneous Klein–Gordon equation of the form

$$U_{tt}(x, t) - U_{xx}(x, t) + U(x, t) = 0 \tag{46}$$

with initial conditions;

$$U(x, 0) = 0, U_t(x, 0) = x. \tag{47}$$

On comparing example three to the general linear Klein-Gordon equation, we get;

$$a = 1, h(x, t) = 0, f(x) = 0 \text{ and } g(x) = x$$

Similarly to example one, on substituting the values of $a, h(x, t), f(x)$ and $g(x)$ into equation (13) and (14) we get;

$$E(U_0(x, t)) = s^2(0) + s^3(x) + s^2E(0) = xs^3 \tag{48}$$

And the recurrence equation becomes

$$E[\sum_0^\infty U_{n+1}(x, t)] = s^2 \frac{d^2}{dx^2} E \sum_0^\infty U_n(x, t) - s^2 E\{\sum_0^\infty U_n(x, t)\} \tag{49}$$

Applying the inverse Elzaki transform to equation (48), we get;

$$U_0(x, t) = E^{-1}(xs^3) = xt \tag{50}$$

Now, we compute the individual term from the recurrence equation (49):

when $n=0$, we get;

$$E\{U_1(x, t)\} = s^2 \frac{d^2}{dx^2} E\{U_0(x, t)\} - s^2 E\{U_0(x, t)\} \tag{51}$$

Substituting equation (48) into equation (51), we get;

$$E\{U_1(x, t)\} = s^2 \frac{d^2}{dx^2} (xs^3) - s^2(xs^3) = -xs^5 \tag{52}$$

Applying the inverse Elzaki transform to equation (52), we get;

$$U_1(x, t) = E^{-1}(-xs^5) = -x \frac{t^3}{3!} \tag{53}$$

when $n=1$, we get;

$$E\{U_2(x, t)\} = s^2 \frac{d^2}{dx^2} E\{U_1(x, t)\} - s^2 E\{U_1(x, t)\} \tag{54}$$

Substituting equation (52) into equation (54), we get;

$$E\{U_2(x, t)\} = s^2 \frac{d^2}{dx^2} (-xs^5) - s^2(-xs^5) = xs^7 \tag{55}$$

Applying the inverse Elzaki transform to equation (55), we get;

$$U_2(x, t) = E^{-1}(xs^7) = x \frac{t^5}{5!} \tag{56}$$

when $n=2$, we get;

$$E\{U_3(x, t)\} = s^2 \frac{d^2}{dx^2} E\{U_2(x, t)\} - s^2 E\{U_2(x, t)\} \tag{57}$$

Substituting equation (55) into equation (57), we get;

$$E\{U_3(x, t)\} = s^2 \frac{d^2}{dx^2} (xs^7) - s^2(xs^7) = -xs^9 \tag{58}$$

Applying the inverse Elzaki transform to equation (58), we get;

$$U_3(x, t) = E^{-1}(-xs^9) = -x \frac{t^7}{7!} \tag{59}$$

Similarly, other terms can be computed. Hence, we have the solution of equation (46) to be

$$\begin{aligned} U(x, t) &= U_0(x, t) + U_1(x, t) + U_2(x, t) + U_3(x, t) + U_4(x, t) + \dots \\ &= xt - x \frac{t^3}{3!} + x \frac{t^5}{5!} - x \frac{t^7}{7!} + x \frac{t^9}{9!} - \dots \\ &= x(t - \frac{t^3}{3!} + \frac{t^5}{5!} - \frac{t^7}{7!} + \frac{t^9}{9!} - \dots) = xsint \end{aligned} \tag{60}$$

Thus, the EADM solution is given as $U(x, t) = xsint$

Table 4: Numerical solution for example 3

$U(x, t)$	Exact solution	EADM solution
-----------	----------------	---------------

0,0	0.0000000000000000	0.0000000000000000
0.2,0.2	0.0397338661590122	0.0397338661590122
0.4,0.4	0.1557673369234600	0.1557673369234600
0.6,0.6	0.3387854840370210	0.3387854840370210
0.8,0.8	0.5738848727196180	0.5738848727196180
1.0,1.0	0.8414709848078970	0.8414709848078970
1.2,1.2	1.1184469031606700	1.1184469031606700
1.4,1.4	1.3796296219838400	1.3796296219838400
1.6,1.6	1.5993177648664100	1.5993177648664100
1.8,1.8	1.7529257355807500	1.7529257355807500
2.0,2.0	1.8185948536513600	1.8185948536513600

Figure 3: Graphical solution of example 3

Example 4 . Consider the non-homogeneous Klein–Gordon equation of the form:

$$U_{tt}(x, t) - U_{xx}(x, t) + U(x, t) = 2\sin x \tag{61}$$

with initial conditions;

$$U(x, 0) = \sin x, U_t(x, 0) = 1. \tag{62}$$

On comparing example four to the general linear Klein-Gordon equation, we get;

$$a = 1, h(x, t) = 2\sin x, f(x) = \sin x \text{ and } g(x) = 1$$

Similarly, on substituting the values of $a, h(x, t), f(x)$ and $g(x)$ into equation (13) and (14) we get;

$$E(U_0(x, t)) = s^2(\sin x) + s^3(1) + s^2 E(2\sin x) = 2s^4 \sin x + s^2 \sin x + s^3 \tag{63}$$

And the recurrence equation becomes

$$E[\sum_0^\infty U_{n+1}(x, t)] = s^2 \frac{d^2}{dx^2} E \sum_0^\infty U_n(x, t) - s^2 E\{\sum_0^\infty U_n(x, t)\} \tag{64}$$

Applying the inverse Elzaki transform to equation (63), we get;

$$U_0(x, t) = E^{-1}(2s^4 \sin x + s^2 \sin x + s^3) = t^2 \sin x + \sin x + t \tag{65}$$

Now, we compute the individual term from the recurrence equation (64):

when n=0, we get;

$$E\{U_1(x, t)\} = s^2 \frac{d^2}{dx^2} E\{U_0(x, t)\} - s^2 E\{U_0(x, t)\} \tag{66}$$

Substituting equation (63) into equation (66), we get;

$$\begin{aligned} E\{U_1(x, t)\} &= s^2 \frac{d^2}{dx^2} (2s^4 \sin x + s^2 \sin x + s^3) - s^2 (2s^4 \sin x + s^2 \sin x + s^3) \\ &= -2s^6 \sin x - s^4 \sin x - 2s^6 \sin x - s^4 \sin x - s^5 = -4s^6 \sin x - 2s^4 \sin x - s^5 \end{aligned} \tag{67}$$

Applying the inverse Elzaki transform to equation (67), we get;

$$U_1(x, t) = E^{-1}(-4s^6 \sin x - 2s^4 \sin x - s^5) = -\frac{t^4}{3!} \sin x - t^2 \sin x - \frac{t^3}{3!} \tag{68}$$

when n=1, we get;

$$E\{U_2(x, t)\} = s^2 \frac{d^2}{dx^2} E\{U_1(x, t)\} - s^2 E\{U_1(x, t)\} \tag{69}$$

Substituting equation (67) into equation (69), we get;

$$\begin{aligned} E\{U_2(x, t)\} &= s^2 \frac{d^2}{dx^2} (-4s^6 \sin x - 2s^4 \sin x - s^5) - s^2 (-4s^6 \sin x - 2s^4 \sin x - s^5) \\ &= 4s^8 \sin x + 2s^6 \sin x + 4s^8 \sin x + 2s^6 \sin x + s^7 = 8s^8 \sin x + 4s^6 \sin x + s^7 \end{aligned} \tag{70}$$

Applying the inverse Elzaki transform to equation (70), we get;

$$U_2(x, t) = E^{-1}(8s^8 \sin x + 4s^6 \sin x + s^7) = \frac{8t^6}{6!} \sin x + \frac{t^4}{3!} \sin x + \frac{t^5}{5!} \tag{71}$$

when n=2, we get;

$$E\{U_3(x, t)\} = s^2 \frac{d^2}{dx^2} E\{U_2(x, t)\} - s^2 E\{U_2(x, t)\} \tag{72}$$

Substituting equation (70) into equation (72), we get;

$$\begin{aligned} E\{U_3(x, t)\} &= s^2 \frac{d^2}{dx^2} (8s^8 \sin x + 4s^6 \sin x + s^7) - s^2 (8s^8 \sin x + 4s^6 \sin x + s^7) \\ &= -8s^{10} \sin x - 4s^8 \sin x - 8s^{10} \sin x - 4s^8 \sin x - s^9 \\ &= -16s^{10} \sin x - 8s^8 \sin x - s^9 \end{aligned} \tag{73}$$

Applying the inverse Elzaki transform to equation (73), we get;

$$U_3(x, t) = E^{-1}(-16s^{10} \sin x - 8s^8 \sin x - s^9) = -\frac{16t^8}{8!} \sin x - \frac{8t^6}{6!} \sin x - \frac{t^7}{7!} \tag{74}$$

Similarly other terms can be computed. We have the solution of equation (60) to be

$$\begin{aligned} U(x, t) &= U_0(x, t) + U_1(x, t) + U_2(x, t) + U_3(x, t) + U_4(x, t) + \dots \\ &= t^2 \sin x + \sin x + t - \frac{t^4}{3!} \sin x - t^2 \sin x - \frac{t^3}{3!} + \frac{8t^6}{6!} \sin x \\ &\quad + \frac{t^4}{3!} \sin x + \frac{t^5}{5!} - \frac{16t^8}{8!} \sin x - \frac{8t^6}{6!} \sin x - \frac{t^7}{7!} \dots \\ &= \sin x + t - \frac{t^3}{3!} + \frac{t^5}{5!} - \frac{t^7}{7!} + \dots = \sin x + \operatorname{sint} \end{aligned} \tag{75}$$

Thus, the EADM solution is given as $U(x, t) = \sin x + \operatorname{sint}$

Table 5: Numerical solution for example 4

$U(x, t)$	Exact solution	EADM solution
0,0	0.000000000000000	0.000000000000000
0.2,0.2	0.397338661590122	0.397338661590122
0.4,0.4	0.778836684617300	0.778836684617300
0.6,0.6	1.129284946790070	1.129284946790070
0.8,0.8	1.434712181799050	1.434712181799050
1.0,1.0	1.682941969615790	1.682941969615790
1.2,1.2	1.864078171934450	1.864078171934450
1.4,1.4	1.970899459976920	1.970899459976920
1.6,1.6	1.999147206083010	1.999147206083010
1.8,1.8	1.947695261756390	1.947695261756390
2.0,2.0	1.818594853651360	1.818594853651360

Figure 4: Graphical solution of example 4

5.0 Conclusion

The Elzaki-Adomian Decomposition Method (EADM) has been demonstrated as an effective approach for obtaining analytical solutions to both homogeneous and non-homogeneous linear Klein-Gordon equations. The integration of the Elzaki transform with the Adomian decomposition method proves to be a powerful combination, enabling the efficient resolution of complex differential equations. The application of EADM to specific cases of the Klein-Gordon equation underscores its versatility and robustness. The method's high rate of convergence significantly enhances its reliability, ensuring that accurate solutions are achieved

with reduced computational effort and time. The results of this study confirm that EADM not only simplifies the process of solving linear Klein-Gordon equations but also provides a highly convergent pathway to accurate analytical solutions. This makes EADM a valuable tool for addressing a wide range of problems involving linear differential equations. Its ability to combine the strengths of the Elzaki transform and the Adomian decomposition method ensures rapid convergence to accurate solutions, making it an indispensable tool for researchers in the field. The study's findings affirm the method's potential to significantly enhance the analytical solving of differential equations, paving the way for future research and applications.

REFERENCES

- Adewale Adedokun, K., Oyedunsi Olayiwola, M., Adedapo Alaje, I., Olarewaju Yunus, A., Olalekan Oladapo, A., & Oyeleye Kareem, K. (2024). A Caputo fractional-order model of tuberculosis incorporating enlightenment and therapy using the Laplace-Adomian decomposition method. *International Journal of Modeling and Simulation*, 1-15.
- Ahmadov, A. I., Nagiyev, S. M., Ikot, A. N., & Tarverdiyeva, V. A. (2024). Analytical solutions for the Klein-Gordon equation with combined exponential type and ring-shaped potentials. *Scientific Reports*, 14(1), 5527.
- Bilal, M., Iqbal, J., Ali, R., Awwad, F. A., & Ismail, E. A. (2024). Establishing breather and N-soliton solutions for conformable Klein-Gordon equation. *Open Physics*, 22(1), 20240044.
- Elzaki, T. M. (2011). The New Integral Transform Elzaki Transform. *Global Journal of Pure and Applied Mathematics*, ISSN 0973-1768 Volume 7, Number 1 (2011), pp. 57-64.
- Emmanuel, I. U., & Idu, H. K. (2024). Analytical Study of the Behavioral Trend of Klein-Gordon Equation in Different Potentials. *Science publishing group*, 13(1), 12-16. <https://doi.org/10.11648/j.ajmp.20241301.12>
- Falade K. I., Tiamiyu A. T. A newly formulated algorithm for the numerical solution of nonlinear Klein-Gordon equation, *Journal of Nigerian Mathematical Society*, the Vol. 41, Issue 1, pp. 13-25, 2022
- Hashim, G. E., Mohammed, H. A., Hajhamed, D. A., & Naga, A. (2023). The separation of variables method for solving the Klein-Gordon equation in curved spacetime. *EPRA International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research (IJMR)*, 9(2), 29-35. <https://doi.org/10.36713/epra12352>.
- Hussein, M. A. (2024). Using the Elzaki decomposition method to solve nonlinear fractional differential equations with the Caputo-Fabrizio fractional operator. *Baghdad Science Journal*, 21(3).
- Ige, O., Oderinu, R., Elzaki, T. (2019). Adomian Polynomial and Elzaki Transform Method of Solving Fifth Order Korteweg-De Vries Equation. *Caspian Journal of Mathematical Sciences (CJMS)*, 8(2):103-119. [doi:10.22080/cjms.2018.14486.1346](https://doi.org/10.22080/cjms.2018.14486.1346)
- Khan, H., Barak, S., Kumam, P., & Arif, M. (2019). Analytical solutions of fractional Klein-Gordon and gas

(Print) ISSN 3027-284X

dynamics equations, via the (G'/G)-expansion method. *Symmetry*, 11(4), 566.

Khuri, S. A. (2001). A Laplace decomposition algorithm applied to a class of nonlinear differential equations. *J Math Appl*. 1(4), 141-155.

Kumar, R. (2022). Investigation for the numerical solution of Klein-Gordon equations using scale 3 Haar wavelets. In *Journal of Physics: Conference Series* (Vol. 2267, No. 1, p. 012152). IOP Publishing.

Mohammad, P., Marzieh, M., & Ali, A. (2024). Numerical estimation of the fractional Klein-Gordon equation with Discrete Chebyshev Polynomials. *Alexandria Engineering Journal*, 90(), 44-53. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aej.2024.01.032>.

Olayiwola, M. O., Alaje, A. I., Yunus, A. O., Adedokun, K. A., & Bashiru, K. A. (2024). A mathematical modeling of COVID-19 treatment strategies utilizing the Laplace Adomian Decomposition method. *Results in Control and Optimization*, 14, 100384.

Onyenegecha, C. P., Opara, A. I., Njoku, I. J., Udensi, S. C., Ukwuihe, U. M., Okereke, C. J., & Omame, A. (2021). Analytical solutions of D-dimensional Klein-Gordon equation with modified Mobius squared potential. *Results in Physics*, 25, 104144.

Orapine, H. O., Baidu, A. A., Oko, G., & Nyamtam, E. V. (2022). Analytical solutions of some special nonlinear partial differential equations Using Elzaki-Adomian decomposition method. *Science*

Online: E-ISSN 3026-9245

World Journal, 17(4), 467-473. <http://www.scienceworldjournal.org>

Srinivasa, K., Mulimani, M., & Adel, W. (2024). A numerical approach for solving nonlinear fractional Klein-Gordon equation with applications in quantum mechanics. *Journal of Nonlinear, Complex and Data Science*, (0).

Yunus, A. O., & Olayiwola, M. O. (2024). The analysis of a novel COVID-19 model with the fractional-order incorporating the impact of the vaccination campaign in Nigeria via the Laplace-Adomian Decomposition Method. *Journal of the Nigerian Society of Physical Sciences*, 1830-1830.